

ARMY WOMEN'S CORPS CAREER DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER EQUALITY ROLES AT ARMY HEADQUARTERS

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Abstract

Gender issues are not a new issue in people's lives. Gender is a construction of social roles based on gender differences which is still ongoing today. In general, gender issues that are clearly visible in human social life are generally shaped by stereotypes against certain gender roles to the issue of discrimination against women. Because basically every individual has the desire to increase their potential and develop their skills in organizations, as well as in the Army Women's Corps, in other words, everyone has the right to develop their careers so that they can fulfill their physiological and self-actualization needs which are increasing day by day along with development of time. The method used in this research is a case study using a qualitative approach, while the results of this study explain that, Kowad in its role in the defense sector has gone through several generations, besides that Kowad also has the same duties and roles in national defense as soldiers. other TNI. The similarity of tasks and roles was not supported by similarities in career development at Kowad. There is a gap in the aspect of role development based on gender equality in career development in Kowad, especially with promotions and placements, even though if viewed from an organizational point of view, the career development given to Kowad today is only limited to expertise in the fields of medicine and law. It is unfortunate considering that so many positions in other fields are given to male soldiers but are not given to female Kowad, meaning that in this case the leadership has not been able to open wider the door for career development for Kowad. AD, which throughout the history of the TNI has never happened, but there are some very unfortunate things in the program. First, the placement and assignment of Taruni graduates today is still not right, because if you look at the other male cadets, they are trained to become Platoon Commanders or Battalion Commanders, but today their assignments are not like the assignments of male soldiers who are actually targeted by leadership as a potential successor to future leaders, meaning that it is considered here that the program is less effective when viewed from the point of view of career development.

Keywords: Career development, Gender equality, Women's Army Corps

A. INTRODUCTION

Career is an important thing that needs to be considered and planned by every individual because career is one of the determinants of success and long-term human survival and career is also the entire position or position that a person may occupy in the organization in his work life, and career goals are the highest position that can be held. will be occupied by someone in an organization. In addition, careers also involve various aspects of life such as education, training, work, family, and many more, the traditional view assumes that a career is only limited to work and then getting paid for the work, but the modern view views that career is a long-term learning and development process. in a sustainable manner in order to prepare

oneself to increase self-values so as to expand opportunities and potential in working in any situation (Andriyanto, 2018).

Career is something different from just a job, because work is something that is done only to earn money, short term, and the effect is not significant for future life, while career is a series of activities that equip a person with long-term and even lifelong experiences and learning. Career development cannot be ignored because it is a vital aspect for individuals and organizations, various technological advances and globalization and current competition force each individual to be active in attitude, improve skills, and develop abilities in order to survive, compete and become superior. In developing a career, many women work to get the highest position, but some empirical research proves that there are still few women reach the highest career position in their career ladder.

Career is a job and the result of training or education that people want to do for a long time which consists of a sequence of experiences or a series of work that is held during a person's life that provides continuity and tranquility so as to create attitudes and behavior. Adjustment for women in order to develop a career is a must considering the obstacles they face tend to be more winding than men, on the other hand women have more roles and responsibilities than men in family management so that it makes it difficult for women to develop careers (Astuti & Purwanta, 2019; Digidowiseiso, 2022).

Career development is an effort to formally and continuously improve employee capabilities both by the individual himself and supported by support from the organization in order to achieve the desired career goals and the availability of employees with the right qualifications to meet the needs of the organization, but in career development the role of women in the world of work is still limited. not stand out yet. Often women only occupy unimportant positions. However, several other studies have identified other challenges such as education, social norms and gender discrimination so that it is difficult for some women to get a position or position in an institution or organization, as well as careers for women in the Indonesian Army.

Women in the Indonesian Armed Forces, especially the Indonesian Army, currently have several distinctive abilities that are able to play a dual role, apart from being housewives, women have higher resilience than men, the results of the study show that in general women are more diligent, efficient and efficient and reliable In order to occupy certain important positions, this strong patrilineal culture is reinforced by religious dogma and cultural heritage that prevails in most parts of the archipelago. family governance so as to be able to ward off social pressure from the surrounding environment. Initially, the TNI began to open up the role of women in the military through the Army, or the Women's Army Corps (Kowad). Kowad in its role in the defense sector has gone through several generations, besides that Kowad also has the same duties and roles in national defense, no different from other TNI soldiers. The similarity of tasks and roles was not supported by similarities in career development at Kowad.

There is a gap in the aspect of role development based on gender equality in career development in Kowad, especially with promotions and placements. Career development supported by career development of Human Resources is still low, it can be seen that the possibility of developing the ability for Kowad within the Indonesian Army has priority as part of non-combat tasks, but there are also those who hold positions as Danramil for certain Regional Command Units (Satkowil). This is Kowad's role for domestic and overseas assignments; Kowad is given the opportunity to get assignments to become delegates to several countries (Effendi, 2018; Suharyono & Digdowiseiso, 2021).

Women's participation in the military always raises pros and cons because the military is identical to men, the study shows that women's participation in the military is often made invisible in the historical records of military institutions, even in some countries, women in the military have always been a minority and placed in the military. services that are more suitable for women, such as in the medical and technical fields, whereas research results show that in general women are more diligent, frugal and efficient and can be relied upon to occupy certain important positions when compared to men. Gender equality in the military in the development of individual careers has not been fully realized, but efforts to get there are always carried out by every Kowad member by increasing their capacity as military soldiers.

Since its inception, the military world has been perceived as a masculine world, so it is synonymous with male domination, synonymous with violence and war, so this perception does not provide equal opportunities for women to participate equally in military service, this perception is systematically considered to marginalize the role of women's military. Individual career development can be seen from nature. One of the factors of differences in the roles and opportunities of women in an institution is the cultural values in a country that still does not believe in the capacity and capability of women in carrying out strategic roles so that it affects the culture of the institution, this has an unfavorable impact on the career development of women in an organization. (Gunaryono, 2009; Sidiq et al., 2020).

The researchers analyzed several factors that limit women from getting to the top positions, namely gender bias, stereotypes, discrimination against women, limited jobs offered to women, and not many opportunities for their career advancement, these factors occur not because of limited skills and capabilities of women. in carrying out work, but because of cultural and social traditions.

Gender equality in the military world will at least only be realized if female and male soldiers are given broad and equal opportunities to compete fairly with other colleagues, and to make this happen requires better gender awareness in every soldier, where men realize that women also have the same abilities as them and accept that there are female soldiers who have a higher strategic position than them. Until now, there is still no firm and detailed regulation on gender equality that can be implemented in accordance with existing regulations regarding development and assignment in the TNI which can be occupied / held by TNI women. On the other hand, TNI women have the skills and competencies to be able to take part in a

professional and professionally proportional field without violating their nature, dignity and worth (Himmawan, 2020).

There is still no specific comprehensive review of career development for Kowad soldiers in achieving the highest military careers and occupying strategic positions, as well as knowing the gender equality strategy for Kowad soldiers at the Army Headquarters, besides some facts show that Kowad soldiers find it difficult to achieve peak careers as male soldiers who have been able to occupy the highest positions, for example there are still no Kowad soldiers who hold Two Star positions and various positions have never been given to Kowad, while women in the sea and air spells have been given these positions, the researcher intends to conduct a search and renewal related to the career development of Kowad at Headquarters, as well as examining the difficulty of reaching the peak of careers for Kowad soldiers at Headquarters so that they can become references and solutions in the future, this is what is expected to be a novelty (novelty) in this study.

B. METHOD

The method used in this research is a case study with a qualitative approach, which is intended to study comprehensively about the background of the problem, the circumstances and position of an event, as well as social interactions that are as they are, the subjects studied are relatively limited, but the variables and focus under study very broad dimensions. The type of data in this study consisted of primary data and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained by researchers directly from the first hand or obtained from respondents through interviews, focus groups and panels or data generated from interviews of researchers with resource persons. The primary data obtained by the author came from several informants including the Assistant for Personnel, Brigadier General Kowad, Colonel Kowad, and Lieutenant Colonel Kowad.

The secondary data is data obtained by researchers from existing sources in the form of notes, documentation, reports and decisions. Researchers get secondary data from records and decisions from military data, especially data related to Kowad. Meanwhile, the data collection techniques used in this study include participation observation, in-depth interviews and documentation. Meanwhile, data analysis is carried out interactively and continues to completion, so that the data becomes saturated, while the activities include data reduction by classifying, directing, removing unnecessary data and organizing data, so that in this way final conclusions can be drawn. drawn. deceived and verified, then the data presentation is carried out with the aim of presenting data on certain targets that are easy to understand and presented in a form that is easy to understand, and finally verify and draw conclusions in accordance with the validity of the data obtained. is the process of data validity to obtain objective data (Izzawati & Lisnawati, 2015; Sidiq et al., 2021).

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Career development for the Women's Army Corps (Kowad) at Army Headquarters

Career planning from the perspective of high-ranking officers is a thought from military members who are very mature because they have been proven to be able to reach high positions so that the statements made by them can have a tremendous impact on the soldiers under them, in addition, they have the authority to analyze and make a policies that can affect the ongoing development of a military career, especially for Kowad. In developing a career individually from the point of view of the leadership of the Personal Assistant (Aspers) Chief of Army Staff as a person who has the authority to raise the rank, Soldiers must be able to show their best, need to work every time, be responsive, tough, willing to be placed and assigned wherever and whenever, may not position yourself as a weak person, need to fight all laziness (Jovani, 2014)

The leadership of Kowad considers that all career opportunities are wide open regardless of whether he is a male or female soldier, the most important thing is whether he wants to prove that he is worthy and suitable to be given the highest rank or not. want to work as hard as other male soldiers, this is a consideration for the leadership not to raise Kowad soldiers, besides that many of Kowad don't want to carry out heavy tasks like men, so if you want to get the highest career you must be able to sacrifice many things such as family and time spent more extra, besides that he must be willing to compete with other male soldiers.

Intermediate Officers have another point of view in individual career development, the first step they need to do is to learn and understand each other's duties, after understanding what needs to be done and completed, they need to be serious in completing any task given by the leadership, it is necessary responsibility, discipline, should not be sluggish, able to maximize self-potential, maximal in carrying out and completing tasks, so that if it is like that, no matter what the leadership will definitely see how their performance is, there is no need to ask for positions such as soldiers will be promoted (Juita , 2011; Prawira et al., 2021).

In addition to working optimally, the strategy of middle-ranking officers in developing their careers is to have the determination to develop themselves, to be willing and able to adapt their abilities to face the rapidly changing times, to be willing to carry out self-development within military organizations and outside organizations such as taking special management courses, as well as attending public lectures outside in order to obtain competent knowledge so that they can carry out their duties while remaining in the appropriate knowledge corridor, if this is the case then these efforts will facilitate the leadership in solving various affairs and organizational problems of the Indonesian Army and it will be easy for the leadership to give the best position. For him.

Women's career development climate is psychologically much different from men's career development. Women need more extra energy to achieve the highest careers compared to men, so like it or not they need to motivate themselves and from within to always think

positively and always complete tasks. Women as a soldier cannot stand alone in developing a career, one of the main factors that determine Kowad's career development is how he can manage time and carry out tasks between organizational tasks and family tasks in a balanced way, if one of them is not balanced then there will be problems which will be very disturbing in career development, therefore the energy expended is more extra compared to men.

Individual career development problems according to Dr. Conie as a military observer generally occurs due to a lack of self-motivation to develop and achieve the ultimate goal as high as possible. For example, there are some Kowad soldiers who are seen by the leadership as having extraordinary skills and abilities which can boost the performance of the Indonesian Army to a higher level so that the leadership promotes them to higher positions. In order to fill the vacant position so that he can develop in another place even though it is far from his place of origin, but the opportunity given is actually ignored by some Kowad soldiers, they tend to prefer to remain silent and work in a place that they think is comfortable, even though for achieving the highest positions and careers requires a high sacrifice of time, energy, and effort, but most of them tend not to want to achieve a better career offered by the leadership not because of their inability but because of their unwillingness (Mas. ita et al., 2019).

However, not every Kowad is lazy to achieve the highest career, as Wara said, that many of the Kowad soldiers can even beat the performance of men, but instead they are not given the opportunity, from an individual point of view they must be able to develop themselves, must see many opportunities, seeing organizational needs and choosing the right career plan in order to fill the vacancies needed by the TNI AD, as an example of the findings he found, namely being given SESKO school rights but not being given position rights like men who graduated from Sesko.

In the opinion of the Air Force Woman (Wara), Kowad must be willing to develop themselves, learn all things about the TNI AD profession, scientific development that is relevant to needs, and want to learn with superiors, many Kowad problems are encountered when holding meetings, where the meeting is a component important in the progress of the organization, they actually joke, even though if they make the wrong decision or misunderstand the decision, it will have fatal consequences for the staff under them. Therefore, each individual must always be serious in carrying out their duties, should not play games and stay focused, must pay attention, live and enjoy the process (Khaerani, 2002).

The Women's Navy Corps (Kowal) is of the opinion that the leadership of the TNI AD needs to improve and evaluate various policies related to career development for KOWAD, she is of the opinion that if the TNI AL and TNI AU can only provide two-star positions, the TNI AD should also be able to, but unfortunately until today there is no Kowad who has served as a Two Star. Regarding the placement of the Two-Star position, she is very sure that in the future there will definitely be someone who can achieve this position and will be able to carry out the mandate of the position given by the leadership, but for TNI women who will later receive the mandate, of course they will have to take responsibility for the mandate seriously.

Indeed, it is necessary to provide proof that Kowad must be able to carry out this task so that in the future there will be many other Kowad who are motivated to achieve the highest position.

If the Organization's policies are still not in favor of the Individual, then Kowad as an individual cannot just wait for the policies handed down by the organization in the context of career development, especially from the perspective of gender equality, Kowad must be able to analyze themselves and find a way out of all problems in order to be able to resolve all cases. And easy to achieve what is expected in career development.

Each individual Kowad must be able to keep up with the times that are constantly changing, because Kowad as a subordinate cannot choose the desired position, place, and position, so what needs to be done is to be maximal in carrying out all tasks, must be able to fill in the deficiencies that exist in themselves and in the Organization, must be able to read the leadership policies carefully in order to be able to follow the path desired by the Organization, if the Kowad soldiers have been proven to be able to solve all problems, the researcher assesses that the Kowad person will reach the highest career peak (Musarovah, 2015).

Before reaching the peak of its career, the organization held recruitment in order to get the best Human Resources (HR) which was expected in the future to be able to help ease the burden on the leadership in operating all TNI Army programs as well as as a regeneration program for future leaders. Kowad is not intended for combat corps, the consideration is the physical limitations of Indonesian women which are far below the physical abilities of men, so the placement of Kowad is limited to the administrative field, namely, Adjutant General, Health, Psychology, Topography, Supplies and Transportation, Law, Engineers, Military Police and Publisher.

Aspers Chief of Army Staff as the policy-holder authority makes a more efficient recruitment system, that the admissions are based on the needs of today's organizations, such as law, doctors, teachers, accountants, technical experts, so that the TNI AD opens the door for scholars as needed by the organization. They considered that graduates who later entered the TNI were in accordance with the majors required by the Army, they were ready-made Human Resources (HR) so that they no longer needed a longer education than other Regular soldiers. The advantage for scholars who enter the TNI in general and the TNI AD in particular is that they immediately get the rank of Second Lieutenant or in other words, their careers begin with First Officers, so that the door for them to achieve the highest career targets is wider open compared to other soldiers. Started his career as a non-commissioned officer and without special skills (Putriana, 2017).

Aspers said that the leadership had opened up the potential for Kowad to compete for the highest position, especially the Two Star, but he suggested that Kowad should give his best, work hard, exert all his potential, try as men try, even need to surpass men in all areas such as mental, physical, performance, thinking, wisdom in order to get the Two Star position.

The researcher considers that if Aspers has said so, then there needs to be maximum efforts made by Kowad in order to prove that Aspers's statement is true and that Kowad is indeed capable of holding a Two-Star position. According to the rules, Kowad's career development path is still based on where he started his career, if he starts from enlisted, then he will be at the maximum rank of non-commissioned officer, if starting from non-commissioned officer a maximum of Lieutenant Colonel, Starting from Akmil or Sepa PK where their initial rank is First Lieutenant then can continue their career up to Two Stars. The perspective of mid-level officers and late First Officers such as Captains, still regrets the regulation, because the position is only seen from the starting point of soldiers starting their careers, they think that ideally in career development it is not necessary to look at where the starting point is to start a career, but look at how competence, capacity, their capabilities in carrying out their duties, how much benefit he has for the Organization as well as in lightening the burden on the leadership (Salebaran & Amini, 2021).

They assessed that apparently there are still many soldiers who come from low career points but have far better quality and competence compared to soldiers who started their careers at a higher level, this should be a concern for leaders in deciding career development policies, not only benefiting soldiers as individuals, however, it is beneficial for the TNI as an organization because it gets superior seeds if you look at career development in terms of their respective abilities. The researcher considered that the suggestion was very good because one of the failures of Kowad to achieve the highest career goals was due to their ignorance of policies and organizational decisions, especially those related to career development steps towards career peaks, the Organization should guide and direct Kowad to always be motivated to achieve peak career by providing facilities and processes that lead to the leadership of Kowad.

Career development strategies, opportunities and development of gender equality roles for the Women's Army Corps (Kowad) at the Army Headquarters (Mabesad)

In career development, career planning is an attempt to identify the needs, aspirations, opportunities for an individual's career, and how to implement human resource development programs to help their careers, career planning is also to realize the requirements, ambitions, targets of an individual, and ways to develop a human resource plan to maintain or develop a career. Organizations can strengthen career planning for employees, which not only provides them with development opportunities and the most potential and build careers towards success, but also stimulates their enthusiasm to maintain their enthusiasm and intention to pursue further careers. their plans and targets by meeting the realities of organizational development, and providing placements for talented people with long-term goals for the organization, as well as providing strong support and protection for workers (Sugiharti, 2019).

Career planning in the development of human resources in an organization is something that needs to be considered and thought about to achieve the highest position in a career for an individual, as well as the progress of the organization. When an individual has a good career

plan, it will provide the best performance for an organization, meaning that the organization will feel the positive impact of employees who look far away from their career development, so both organizations and individuals need to be able to support each other in the development of human resources.

Before thinking about career planning, organizations need to make the best recruitment system in order to get the best human resources, the main purpose of recruitment is to find qualified applicants who will boost the progress of the organization, therefore underqualified individuals who have the potential to be expelled in the future as well as individuals who overqualified who will suffer frustration and leave the Organization, may not be appointed as employees. From this statement, it is related to the Women's Army Corps, the TNI Headquarters needs to conduct recruitment according to the potential, needs and goals of the Organization so that in long-term planning the soldiers will boost the TNI Organization to be even better and also be able to develop themselves and careers in the TNI Organization (Sulasmi, 2021).

Career development in an organization should be viewed as a very dynamic process that tries to meet the needs of the leader, subordinates and the organization. Career development is also the responsibility of the leadership in encouraging employees to take responsibility for their own careers, career development is also continuous assistance in the form of feedback or individual performance. Besides that, career development should not only be done to a few people who are elected or to people who are in positions or positions.

The TNI AD in the technical manual on career development of TNI AD officers provides an overview of the various steps and stages of career development for TNI AD soldiers in fulfilling the norms of position, rank and education in order to gain capacity, capability, ability, expertise, and thoughts that are qualified in solve complex problems in the TNI AD so that it can make it easier for leaders to complete the tasks of the TNI AD Organization, after it is felt that the soldiers' abilities are quite capable and proven to be able to carry out their duties successfully and well, the TNI AD Organization provides opportunities for soldiers to develop their careers in the army. TNI so that they get the best position they want (Tarigan, 2021).

Various efforts were made through policies, institutions, strengthening of human resources (HR), infrastructure in the field of education in order to improve the quality of human resources for the best soldiers in all areas of the task force, both combat and non-combat for First Officers, Middle Officers, and Higher Officers. The most basic of career development in an organization is how the organizational policies are and how are the steps for planning a soldier's career to reach the highest position, the article is that there are various cases where individuals have made all efforts such as careful career planning, undergoing organizational procedures in an orderly manner, following the stages internal and external career support education, but still collided with the Organization's policies that do not allow soldiers to develop careers in the Organization, then the next case is when the Organization has opened

the door to career development as wide as possible but from individuals themselves, they ignore and do not take advantage of the great opportunities that have been opened by the Organization to achieve the highest position achievement targets so that the Kowad does not advance due to the unwillingness and inability of individuals to develop their careers and positions.

Career development is a process carried out by a Kowad to occupy a position in the future. To support the process of career development, Kowad are required to attend promotion schools. Career development is meant as a result of knowledge, skills, and behavior that will be used to improve the ability of employees to meet job requirements and demands. Career development or promotion is supported by the requirements that must be met including position, service period, military education, training , promotion test (UKP). The promotion test is carried out through a physical refresher graduation exam (garjas), and is one of the mandatory requirements that must be met in the proposed promotion by achieving values that meet the criteria according to age categories (Widiyani, 2010).

Gender issues are one of the problems of Kowad career development at Headquarters, this is due to the non-fulfillment of positions for Kowad that they should be able and have the capacity to carry out the tasks assigned by the leadership as given to male soldiers, so that the opportunities possessed by Kowad are very good. slightly when compared to male soldiers, this is one of the biggest factors that influence the career development of kowad especially when it is associated with gender equality. The career development strategy from the perspective of developing gender equality roles is very interesting to discuss because it has an unusually sharp but varied variety of opinions, The results of the most objective interviews regarding career development and gender equality lead to middle officers, this is because Middle Officers occupy intermediate ranks and positions between policy makers, policy implementers, and administrators. watch out for wisdom so that their task is quite complex, their opinion in this matter can be a criticism and can also be an assessment of how the continuation of Kowad's career development at the Army Headquarters.

The most striking discussion raised by some middle-ranking officers was regarding the elimination of virginity for prospective female soldiers in the Army, this gave rise to several pro and contra opinions due to this policy. The reason for the Middle Officers who supported the elimination of virginity from the Kowad entrance test was to prevent social jealousy between men and women, meaning that the leadership gave the door as wide as possible for any woman to join the TNI AD without any social discrimination, but the reason for those who refused is that virginity is a sign that she is a good woman who always maintains her honor, it tends to be said that the woman is easy to educate and adapt to a harsh military education which forges a soldier from having an ordinary civilian character to a military character who is willing to obey and be loyal to maintain the honor of the nation, how can it be possible to maintain the honor of the nation while maintaining the honor of oneself is still not optimal (Wuriyan, 2019).

All types of recruitment tests given to Kowad candidates are equated with male TNI candidates, such as physical tests, health tests, and psychological tests, from these types of tests, it can be concluded that the leadership does not distinguish between male and female entrance tests, meaning that in the recruitment stage there is still no there are gender equality issues. In order to improve the quality of the TNI AD to keep up with the times, Kowad opened a new route, namely talented students from superior schools, good at foreign languages, excelling in sports, and other fields that are Kowad's priorities. Students from this pathway are proven to be able to fill organizational needs in easing the tasks of leaders who are required to continue to improve the skills and quality of the TNI, especially in an era that continues to change rapidly. For example, if a soldier is proficient in English, he will be given convenience in developing his career, and will even be given scholarships for overseas schools to boost the performance of the Indonesian Army in order to develop international competitiveness.

In the background of career planning, mid-level officers agree that however female soldiers cannot enter or develop careers in the field of combat, such as infantry and artillery so that Kowad is more likely to occupy administrative positions to assist the leadership, but these differences do not reduce the leadership's attention in developing Kowad's career. In other fields, there are several Kowad positions which in terms of promotion are faster than men, meaning that in the context of the difference between combat and administrative positions, each has the same important role and career development, but only in different placements. In an interview with Aspers Chief of Army Staff, he said that the TNI AD is really open to anyone who wants to target the highest career, especially in a two-star position regardless of whether he is a woman or a man, but the thing that needs to be considered is how the soldier prepares himself to adapt to worthy to sit in the highest position, meaning that the leadership does not want to be careless in choosing candidates who will fill strategic positions, especially for Kowad (Cahyani & Sari, 2021).

Aspers Chief of Army Staff said that if Kowad was indeed ready to be placed in that position, the most important thing was to show the leadership that he was able to compete and even outperform other male soldiers. has not been able to show the leadership that he is able to work and defeat male soldiers, if it is deemed appropriate enough even above the average soldier then he will not think long he will be promoted to that position.

Paban Jahril sees it from a male perspective, that he regrets very much because Kowad is still thinking about a career, but neglects his natural duty as a woman, which is to take care of families such as husbands and children, and some of them even forget to get married. According to the researcher, the view of the leadership regarding household and career is wrong, the article is after all that it is the right of the soldier to choose a career up to the highest career or he takes care of the family, because it is a personal realm that cannot be entered by anyone, even superiors. The most important thing in developing a career is how he prioritizes goals by being willing to sacrifice some matters but by compromising and discussing with his family in a healthy and good manner in order to get common ground and

support, as a result of the need to consider and discuss career development with his husband, Army women in general unable to achieve an optimal career (Indriyani et al., 2020).

From an organizational point of view, the career development given to Kowad today is only limited to expertise in the fields of medicine and law, which is very unfortunate considering that so many positions in other fields were given to male soldiers but were not given to Kowad, meaning in this case the leadership still not able to open the door wider for career development for Kowad. Some time ago the leadership of the TNI AD had started to open an Army Taruni which has never happened in the history of the TNI, but there are some things that are very unfortunate in the program. First, the placement and assignment of Taruni graduates today is still not right, because if you look at the other male cadets, they are trained to become Platoon Commanders or Battalion Commanders, but today their assignments are not like the assignments of male soldiers who are actually targeted by the leader as a potential successor to future leaders, meaning that it is considered here that the program is less effective when viewed from the point of view of career development (Martanti, 2006).

The second problem is that today the Army Taruni program has been abolished, even though the Air Force and Navy are still open for recruitment from the Taruni route, from this situation it can be said that there are still differences in attitudes towards Kowad and Men in terms of recruitment, career development, and final career. From some of the findings in the field, the researcher sees that there is still a lack of direct attention from the leadership to Kowad in providing opportunities for Kowad's career development related to gender equality.

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the identification of problems, research results, and discussions described previously, it can be concluded as follows, the leadership of the Indonesian Army will open the widest possible career development for Kowad and will provide the same opportunities as male soldiers. The leadership's point of view is that Kowad still has not shown the best efforts and achievements for the organization so that it can be considered worthy of being given career development to the peak of a career like men, most of them are still not ready to compete mentally, physically, and psychologically with male soldiers, so there is still no seriousness In trying to develop a career to the highest career peak, Kowad soldiers should show and prove that they are able to compete with all male soldiers so that the leadership will facilitate the development of Kowad's career to the peak of a career.

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